

Vachellia xanthophloea

Fever tree

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 15-25 meters (height)

Distribution:

They are found in the Western Cape, Limpopo, KwaZulu-Natal, and Mpumalanga provinces of South Africa.

Importance:

This indigenous tree species is important due to its resistance to the polyphagous shot hole borer (PSHB), as recognised in the 2023 FABI replant list. Sequencing its genome could reveal the mechanisms underlying this resistance, inform conservation strategies, and contribute to understanding PSHB risk to South African tree biodiversity.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 82.2 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 19.85 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.66 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.1% [Single: 37.6%, Duplicated: 60.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 361.27 kilobases

Contig number: 6 580

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